

TOURISTS' SATISFACTION AND EXPENDITURES AMIDST NEW NORMAL

Francis Ivan S. Cosare, John David T. Maluenda,
Nigel Tim Sean A. Maratas, Jhon Andrew M. Suarez,
Leuc Francois Trotin, Billy O. Cosares

*Bohol Wisdom School College of Education
CPG North Avenue, Tagbilaran City, Bohol, Philippines*

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.12663320>

ABSTRACT

The main purpose of this study was to investigate tourist satisfaction and expenditures in Panglao, Bohol, Philippines, amidst the new normal brought about by the COVID-19 pandemic. The research aims to profile tourists based on age, gender, and nationality, assess their satisfaction levels, analyze their expenditures, and explore the relationship between satisfaction and expenditures. Utilizing a quantitative research design, data were gathered through surveys distributed to tourists at Alona Beach. The study revealed that most tourists were young adults (18-35 years), with a balanced gender distribution, and primarily composed of Filipinos, Americans, and Koreans. Findings indicated high overall satisfaction with Panglao, attributed to its appealing tourist attractions, although improvements were suggested in accommodations and transportation. Korean tourists reported highly favorable experiences, while American tourists highlighted the affordability of transportation and the potential for enhanced souvenir offerings. Expenditures were found to be satisfactory across nationalities, emphasizing the region's value proposition. A significant correlation was found between tourist satisfaction and expenditures, underscoring the impact of travel experiences on spending behaviors. Based on these insights, recommendations include upgrading transportation systems, adopting tiered pricing for various budgets, embracing sustainable tourism practices, and promoting cultural activities to enhance the overall tourist experience and stimulate local economic growth. This study contributes valuable knowledge for local authorities and businesses in Panglao to refine their strategies, ensuring an enriched tourist experience and fostering the region's sustainable development.

Keywords: *Expenditures, New Normal, Panglao, Bohol, Satisfaction, Tourism*

INTRODUCTION

Bohol, known for its unique land and water formations, is a popular tourist destination that significantly boosts the local economy. The province offers a range of attractions and souvenirs, from keychains to clothing, which contribute to its economic vitality. However, in the new normal, concerns have arisen about tourist expenditures. Complaints about high costs have increased, prompting the Department of Environment and Natural Resources Central Visayas (DENR-7) to investigate the pricing practices of local governments in Panglao and Bohol (Macasero, 2022).

The COVID-19 pandemic has worsened these issues by negatively impacting businesses, increasing operational costs, and reducing sales (Estremera, n.d.). Enterprises have raised prices to recover from the pandemic's economic fallout, leading to a perception of decreased value among tourists.

In 2020, the Department of Tourism reported an average daily expenditure of approximately 6.8 thousand Philippine Pesos per foreign tourist, despite a sharp decline in tourism arrivals due to travel restrictions (Department of Tourism, 2021).

Research indicates that tourists value quality, price, emotional, and social factors, all of which influence their satisfaction and likelihood to return or recommend the destination to others. Relevant legislative frameworks, such as the Consumers Act of the Philippines (Republic Act No. 7394) and the Tourism Act of 2009 (Republic Act No. Risk Management of Quick Service), emphasize the protection of consumer rights, the provision of high-quality services, and the promotion of sustainable tourism practices.

Ensuring tourists' satisfaction and fair treatment under these regulations is essential for the industry's growth. Factors such as service quality, cleanliness, safety, and accessibility significantly influence satisfaction levels (Rohman, 2020). The competitive dynamics of the tourism sector underscore the importance of understanding pre-purchase attributes and their impact on tourist satisfaction (Ledesma et al., 2022).

This study aims to measure tourist satisfaction and expenditures in Bohol amidst the new normal. By assessing the current levels of tourist satisfaction and analyzing the expenditures of tourists and the factors influencing these expenditures, this research seeks to provide insights into how the tourism industry in Bohol can enhance service quality and value. Understanding these aspects is more critical than ever as the tourism industry navigates the challenges of the new normal. The findings aim to help stakeholders in Bohol improve their offerings, ensuring sustainable growth and a thriving tourism sector in the post-pandemic era.

Research Questions

The researchers aimed to find out the tourist satisfactions and expenditures amidst the new normal in Panglao, Bohol.

Specifically, this study sought to answer the following questions:

1. What is the tourists' profile in terms of:
 - 1.1 age;
 - 1.2 gender; and
 - 1.3 nationality?
2. What is the tourists' profile regarding satisfaction in Panglao?
3. What is the tourists' profile on expenditure in Panglao?
4. Is there a significant relationship between tourists' satisfaction and expenditures amidst the new normal?
5. What improvement plan could be proposed based on the findings of the study?

METHODOLOGY

This section focused on the methodology that was utilized in the conduct of the study. This also outlined the research design, the procedure that was followed, the process of collecting the data and the analysis. During the collection process, the ethical consideration was also discussed.

Research Design

The researchers conducted quantitative surveys to achieve the study's goals of understanding tourist satisfaction and expenditures in Panglao, Bohol. Direct participation from both researchers and respondents gathered specific and detailed information, which was meticulously checked and thoroughly analyzed. The findings enabled the researchers to make a scientific interpretation based on the data collected.

Research Environment and Research Participants

This study was conducted in Panglao, a popular public beach situated at the southwest tip of Panglao Island, Bohol, Philippines. It is renowned for its white sand, rocky cliffs, and commercial facilities that line the one kilometer stretch of the beach. Located near a coral reef, Panglao is also a favored spot for scuba diving and snorkeling. The participants of this study were the tourists at Alona Beach, Panglao, Bohol, who were available on the day the study was conducted.

Table 1
Distribution of Respondents
(N=180)

Nationality	No. of Respondents
Filipino	89
American	36
Korean	55
Total	180

Research Instrument

This study was conducted using a self-made questionnaire to assess tourists' satisfaction and expenditures in Panglao. The questionnaire was developed based on theories from existing research studies and was designed to capture necessary data for the study. Prior to distribution, the researchers piloted the questionnaire to ensure its effectiveness. It included questions about tourists' overall satisfaction with their stay in Panglao, their expenditures during the trip, and their opinions regarding the impact of the COVID-19 pandemic on their experience. Additionally, demographic questions such as age, gender, and nationality were included.

Data Gathering Procedure

The researchers sent a formal letter to the Municipal Mayor of Panglao, requesting permission to conduct a survey in the popular Alona Beach area. The researchers proceeded with the project only after obtaining approval from their adviser and the High School Principal. Once all necessary approvals were secured, the researchers distributed questionnaires to selected respondents, allowing them sufficient time to respond.

Data Analysis

The following treatment was used in the data analysis. The responses were compiled, tabulated, and tallied. To determine the profile of the respondents in terms of age, gender, and nationality, the researchers employed the percentage formula.

$$P = \frac{f}{n} \times 100\%$$

Where:

P = simple percentage

f = frequency

In determining the respondents' profile on satisfaction in Panglao and their profile on expenditures, the Weighted Mean was used.

$$WM = \frac{\sum fx}{N}$$

Where:

WM = Weighted Mean

fx = summation of frequency of scale x

N = number of cases

Meanwhile, to determine the significant relationship between the respondents' satisfaction and expenditures amidst the new normal, the Pearson Product Moment Coefficient of Correlation was utilized.

$$r = \frac{n(\sum xy) - (\sum x)(\sum y)}{\sqrt{[n\sum x^2 - (\sum x)^2][n\sum y^2 - (\sum y)^2]}}$$

Where:

r = the Pearson Product Moment Coefficient of Correlation

n = sample size

$\sum xy$ = the sum of the product of x and y

$\sum x$ = summation of x

$\sum y$ = summation of y

$\sum x^2$ = sum of the squares of x

$\sum y^2$ = sum of the squares of y

RESULTS

This chapter presents, analyzes, and interprets the data regarding the research question. The gathered data are tallied and presented in tabulated, textual, and graphical forms, and analyzed in the context of the variables examined in this study.

The first part focuses on profiling respondents in terms of age, nationality, and gender. The second part presents data concerning respondents' satisfaction with expenditures and their overall satisfaction amidst the new normal. The last part discusses data related to significant differences in respondents' perceptions of their satisfaction amidst the new normal.

Figure 2. Respondents' Profile on Age (N=180)

Figure 2 presents the respondents' profile on age. As shown in the figure, the ages 26 to 35 years old obtained the highest percentage of 45%, while the ages 50 and above years old obtained the lowest percentage of 3%. This indicates that the majority of respondents in the study fall within the 26 to 35 age group, with a smaller proportion of respondents aged 50 and above.

According to (Department of Tourism, 2022) regarding travel behavior among Filipinos. It examines a wide range of age groups, spanning from younger to older individuals, indicating that travel is a common activity across different generations in the Philippines. The study reports that, on average, Filipinos in the surveyed population make trips relatively frequently, suggesting that travel is not just an occasional activity but is a common practice among Filipinos. Furthermore, the primary purpose of these trips is identified as leisure, indicating that a significant proportion of travelers engage in recreational travel for purposes such as vacations or tourism.

Figure 3. Respondents' Profile on Gender (N=180)

Figure 3 reveals the respondents' profile on gender. It showed that 52% of the participants identified as males, while the remaining 48% identified as females. This indicates that there was a slight majority of male respondents in the study, with a slightly smaller proportion of female respondents.

According to Martin (2020), tourist satisfaction is not uniform and varies based on gender-related preferences and expectations. For instance, safety concerns and travel choices may differ between male and female tourists in the Philippines, impacting their overall satisfaction. Service providers and destination marketers in the country should consider these gender-specific factors to tailor their offerings and enhance the satisfaction of all tourists in the post-pandemic tourism environment.

Figure 4. Respondents' Profile on Nationality (N=180)

Figure 4 shows the respondents' profile on nationality. It is revealed that 49% were Filipinos, while 20% were Americans. This indicates that most of the respondents'

nationality were Filipinos. This may be due to the fact that this research is conducted in the Philippines, and most of the population are Filipinos which restricts the diversity of the nationalities of the respondents.

The significant increase in both foreign and local tourist arrivals in Bohol is indicative of a substantial potential boost in tourist expenditure within the region. This surge in arrivals, particularly from South Korea, underscores a strong and consistent flow of spending on accommodations, dining, transportation, and leisure activities. Such expenditure can significantly contribute to the economic growth and sustainability of Bohol's tourism industry (Bohol Tourist Arrivals up by 129% in First 5 Months, 2023).

Table 2
Tourists' Satisfaction Amidst New Normal (N=180)

Statements	WM	DV	RANK
1. The overall travel experience is satisfactory.	4.70	Very Satisfied	1
2. I am satisfied with the accommodations I stayed at during my trip.	4.60	Very Satisfied	6.5
3. The availability of food options made me satisfied.	4.57	Very Satisfied	9
4. The level of customer service I received was satisfactory.	4.61	Very Satisfied	3.5
5. My trip was so satisfactory that I would recommend it to others.	4.59	Very Satisfied	8
6. The trip was satisfactory enough that I would come back here for another trip.	4.60	Very Satisfied	6.5
7. The availability of transportation options are satisfactory.	4.54	Very Satisfied	10
8. The cleanliness and maintenance of the places I visited made me satisfied.	4.61	Very Satisfied	3.5
9. I am satisfied with the use of money during my trip in Panglao.	4.61	Very Satisfied	3.5
10. The safety measures implemented in Panglao is satisfactory.	4.64	Very Satisfied	2
Composite Mean	4.61	Very Satisfied	

Legend:

4.20-5.00 - Very Satisfied

3.40-4.19 - Satisfied

2.60-3.39 - Neutral

1.80-2.59 - Dissatisfied

1.00-1.79 - Very Dissatisfied

Table 2 shows Tourists' Satisfaction Amidst New Normal. Notably, Statement 1, 'The overall travel experience is satisfactory,' garnered the highest weighted mean of 4.70, indicating that respondents are 'Very Satisfied' with their travel experience. Conversely, Statement 7, 'The availability of transportation options is satisfactory,' achieved the lowest weighted mean of 4.54, although it still signifies that respondents are 'Very Satisfied' with transportation options. The overall weighted mean for all statements stands at 4.61, characterized as 'Very Satisfied.' This implies Panglao as an exceptionally attractive tourist destination.

This positive impression is likely to result in glowing reviews and enthusiastic recommendations, potentially driving increased visitor numbers.

Tourist satisfaction continues to hold a pivotal position as a marketing tool. In the evolving landscape of tourism, tourist satisfaction is more critical than ever. It represents the joy experienced by tourists, serving as a clear indicator of their overall satisfaction. As tourists relish their visits in this transformed environment, their contentment becomes a significant factor influencing their decisions to return for future visits (Fatmawati & Olga, 2023).

Table 3
Tourists' Expenditures Amidst New Normal (N=180)

Statements	WM	DV	RANK
1. The reasonable food prices make me satisfied.	4.56	Very Satisfied	5
2. The affordability of transportation to Panglao compared to other tourist destinations leaves me satisfied.	4.31	Very Satisfied	10
3. The fairness of pricing for buying gifts/souvenirs here is satisfactory.	4.47	Very Satisfied	9
4. The prices of hotels left me satisfied.	4.53	Very Satisfied	7
5. The cost of island hopping is what I am satisfied with.	4.52	Very Satisfied	8
6. The favorable pricing of additional offers and handcraft products at this tourist destination satisfies me.	4.55	Very Satisfied	6
7. Staying at Panglao is worth every peso paid.	4.62	Very Satisfied	3.5
8. The nature of services makes me find them satisfying.	4.62	Very Satisfied	3.5
9. The belief that Panglao values my money and offers fair pricing is what I find.	4.63	Very Satisfied	2
10. I am satisfied with my overall stay.	4.66	Very Satisfied	1
Composite Mean	4.55	Very Satisfied	

Legend:

4.20-5.00 - Very Satisfied

3.40-4.19 - Satisfied

2.60-3.39 - Neutral

1.80-2.59 - Dissatisfied

1.00-1.79 - Very Dissatisfied

Table 3 shows Tourists' Expenditures Amidst New Normal. Data revealed that statement 2, "The affordability of transportation to Panglao compared to other tourist destinations leaves me satisfied," received a weighted mean of 4.31, placing it as the lowest scoring. On the other hand, statement 10, "I am satisfied with my overall stay", received the highest with a weighted mean of 4.66. Despite being the lowest score, it's still labeled as "Very Satisfied," indicating a high level of satisfaction. While slightly lower

than other statements, overall sentiment is positive. Respondents found Panglao's transportation affordability relative to other tourist destinations satisfactory.

Tourists will try to reduce their travel expenses either by targeting more affordable destinations, seeking special offers or shortening the length of their stay. In relation to this study, tourists would be more cautious about their travel spending as a result of the economic crisis. Thus, even after the crisis, it is critical to consider attractively priced offers that may seduce and attract tourists as long as the offer is tailored to their financial situation (Estremera, 2020).

Table 4
Satisfaction of Filipino Tourists' Amidst New Normal
(N=89)

Statements	WM	DV	RANK
1. The overall travel experience is satisfactory.	4.74	Very Satisfied	1
2. I am satisfied with the accommodations I stayed at during my trip	4.58	Very Satisfied	8.5
3. The availability of food options made me satisfied.	4.60	Very Satisfied	5.5
4. The level of customer service I received was satisfactory.	4.65	Very Satisfied	2
5. My trip was so satisfactory that I would recommend it to others.	4.58	Very Satisfied	8.5
6. The trip was satisfactory enough that I would come back here for another trip.	4.64	Very Satisfied	3
7. The availability of transportation options are satisfactory.	4.58	Very Satisfied	8.5
8. The cleanliness and maintenance of the places I visited made me satisfied.	4.60	Very Satisfied	5.5
9. I am satisfied with the use of money during my trip in Panglao.	4.60	Very Satisfied	5.5
10. The safety measures implemented in Panglao is satisfactory.	4.61	Very Satisfied	4
Composite Mean	4.62	Very Satisfied	

Legend:

4.20-5.00 - Very Satisfied

3.40-4.19 - Satisfied

2.60-3.39 - Neutral

1.80-2.59 - Dissatisfied

1.00-1.79 - Very Dissatisfied

Table 4 shows Tourists' Satisfaction of Filipinos Amidst the New Normal. Data revealed that statement 1, "The overall travel experience is satisfactory," received a weighted mean of 4.74, indicating the highest level of satisfaction among respondents. While the lowest weighted mean is statement 2, "I am satisfied with the accommodations I stayed at during my trip," statement 5, "My trip was so satisfactory that I would recommend it to others," and statement 7, "The availability of transportation options are satisfactory," gaining weighted mean of 4.58.

The overall weighted mean of 4.62 suggests that while tourists in the Philippines generally express a high level of overall satisfaction with their experiences during the new normal, but there is room for improvement in areas such as accommodations, transportation, and recommendations to others.

The satisfaction of tourists visiting the Philippines is an essential factor in the growth of tourism in the region.

Therefore, it is crucial to ensure that tourists visiting the Philippines are satisfied with their experience. This can be achieved by providing quality services and products that meet their needs and expectations. By doing so, we can increase their satisfaction levels and encourage them to revisit in the future (Gök & Sayın, 2015).

Table 5
Expenditures of Filipino Tourists' Amidst New Normal
(N=89)

Statements	WM	DV	RANK
1. The reasonable food prices make me satisfied.	4.58	Very Satisfied	4.5
2. The affordability of transportation to Panglao compared to other tourist destinations leaves me satisfied.	4.24	Very Satisfied	10
3. The fairness of pricing for buying gifts/souvenirs here is satisfactory.	4.52	Very Satisfied	7.5
4. The prices of hotels left me satisfied.	4.49	Very Satisfied	9
5. The cost of island hopping is what I am satisfied with.	4.52	Very Satisfied	7.5
6. The favorable pricing of additional offers and handcraft products at this tourist destination satisfies me.	4.53	Very Satisfied	6
7. Staying at Panglao is worth every peso paid.	4.64	Very Satisfied	3
8. The nature of services makes me find them satisfying.	4.69	Very Satisfied	1
9. The belief that Panglao values my money and offers fair pricing is what I find.	4.58	Very Satisfied	4.5
10. I am satisfied with my overall stay.	4.66	Very Satisfied	2
Composite Mean	4.55	Very Satisfied	

Legend:

4.20-5.00 - Very Satisfied

3.40-4.19 - Satisfied

2.60-3.39 - Neutral

1.80-2.59 - Dissatisfied

1.00-1.79 - Very Dissatisfied

Table 5 shows the Expenditures of Filipino Tourists' Amidst New Normal. Among the statements, Statement 8, 'The nature of services makes me find them satisfying,' obtained the highest weighted mean of 4.69, indicating that respondents are 'Very Satisfied' with the quality of services. Conversely, Statement 2, 'The affordability of transportation to Panglao compared to other tourist destinations leaves me satisfied,' received the lowest weighted mean of 4.24, suggesting that respondents are 'Very Satisfied,' although to a slightly lesser extent. The Composite Mean for all statements is 4.55, with a descriptive value of 'Very Satisfied,' implying that, overall, tourists are leaving with positive impressions of their experiences, which can enhance Panglao's reputation as a tourist destination.

According to the Philippine News Agency (2023), the Department of Tourism (DOH) has set ambitious goals for 2023, aiming to attract a substantial number of visitors and generate significant revenue. The article also mentions that the Philippines exceeded its arrivals target for 2022, indicating a growing tourism industry with the potential to contribute significantly to the country's economy.

Table 6 Satisfaction of Korean Tourists' Amidst New Normal (N=36)

Statements	WM	DV	RANK
1. The overall travel experience is satisfactory.	4.71	Very Satisfied	1
2. I am satisfied with the accommodations I stayed at during my trip	4.67	Very Satisfied	3.5
3. The availability of food options made me satisfied.	4.55	Very Satisfied	9
4. The level of customer service I received was satisfactory.	4.60	Very Satisfied	6.5
5. My trip was so satisfactory that I would recommend it to others.	4.65	Very Satisfied	5
6. The trip was satisfactory enough that I would come back here for another trip.	4.60	Very Satisfied	6.5
7. The availability of transportation options are satisfactory.	4.49	Very Satisfied	10
8. The cleanliness and maintenance of the places I visited made me satisfied.	4.58	Very Satisfied	8
9. I am satisfied with the use of money during my trip in Panglao.	4.67	Very Satisfied	3.5
10. The safety measures implemented in Panglao is satisfactory.	4.69	Very Satisfied	2
Composite Mean	4.62	Very Satisfied	

Legend:

4.20-5.00 - Very Satisfied

3.40-4.19 - Satisfied

2.60-3.39 - Neutral

1.80-2.59 - Dissatisfied

1.00-1.79 - Very Dissatisfied

Table 6 shows the Satisfaction of Korean Tourists' Amidst New Normal. Notably, Statement 1, 'The overall travel experience is satisfactory,' garnered the highest weighted

mean of 4.71, signaling that respondents are 'Very Satisfied' with the entirety of their travel experience. This signifies an overwhelmingly positive impression of Panglao as a tourist destination. On the other hand, Statement 7, 'The availability of transportation options is satisfactory,' received the lowest weighted mean of 4.49. While this indicates a degree of satisfaction, there is room for potential improvements in transportation offerings to further elevate the tourist experience. The Composite Mean for all statements is an impressive 4.62, with a descriptive value of 'Very Satisfied.' This implies that Korean tourists have immensely enjoyed their stay, likely contributing to positive reviews and potential return visits.

With more tourism products and services available in tourist destinations to serve an increasing number of tourists, there is a tendency for mass tourism to develop because of higher tourism density. This may pose threats to sustainability and increase pandemic susceptibility undermining safety, which may lead to a decline in experience, satisfaction, and commendations (Roxas et al., 2020).

Table 7
Expenditures of Korean Tourists' Amidst New Normal
(N=36)

Statements	WM	DV	RANK
1. The reasonable food prices make me satisfied.	4.58	Very Satisfied	6.5
2. The affordability of transportation to Panglao compared to other tourist destinations leaves me satisfied.	4.40	Very Satisfied	10
3. The fairness of pricing for buying gifts/souvenirs here is satisfactory.	4.49	Very Satisfied	9
4. The prices of hotels left me satisfied.	4.58	Very Satisfied	6.5
5. The cost of island hopping is what I am satisfied with.	4.55	Very Satisfied	8
6. The favorable pricing of additional offers and handcraft products at this tourist destination satisfies me.	4.60	Very Satisfied	5
7. Staying at Panglao is worth every peso paid.	4.62	Very Satisfied	4
8. The nature of services makes me find them satisfying.	4.65	Very Satisfied	3
9. The belief that Panglao values my money and offers fair pricing is what I find.	4.75	Very Satisfied	1
10. I am satisfied with my overall stay.	4.71	Very Satisfied	2
Composite Mean	4.60	Very Satisfied	

Legend:

4.20-5.00 - Very Satisfied

3.40-4.19 - Satisfied

2.60-3.39 - Neutral

1.80-2.59 - Dissatisfied

1.00-1.79 - Very Dissatisfied

Table 7 shows the Expenditures of Korean Tourists' Amidst New Normal. Among the statements, Statement 9, 'The belief that Panglao values my money and offers fair pricing is what I find,' achieved the highest weighted mean of 4.75, signifying a 'Very Satisfied' rating. In contrast, Statement 2, 'The affordability of transportation to Panglao compared to other tourist destinations leaves me satisfied,' received the lowest weighted mean of 4.40, although still indicating 'Very Satisfied' sentiments among respondents. The overall weighted mean for all statements is 4.60, with a descriptive value of 'Very Satisfied.' This implies that Panglao's reputation for transparent and reasonable pricing is a significant asset, likely fostering trust and loyalty among tourists.

According to the Philippine Statistics Authority (2023), data from 2021 to 2022 reflects significant growth in both inbound and domestic tourism expenditure in the Philippines. This upward trend is a promising sign for the country's tourism industry. In conclusion of the study, by analyzing tourist expenditures during this period, valuable insights can be gained to identify areas for improvement and ultimately enhance overall tourist satisfaction.

Table 8
Satisfaction of American Tourists' Amidst New Normal
(N=55)

Statements	WM	DV	RANK
1. The overall travel experience is satisfactory.	4.58	Very Satisfied	3
2. I am satisfied with the accommodations I stayed at during my trip.	4.42	Very Satisfied	10
3. The availability of food options made me satisfied.	4.56	Very Satisfied	4.5
4. The level of customer service I received was satisfactory.	4.53	Very Satisfied	6.5
5. My trip was so satisfactory that I would recommend it to others.	4.53	Very Satisfied	6.5
6. The trip was satisfactory enough that I would come back here for another trip.	4.50	Very Satisfied	9
7. The availability of transportation options are satisfactory.	4.53	Very Satisfied	6.5
8. The cleanliness and maintenance of the places I visited made me satisfied.	4.69	Very Satisfied	1
9. I am satisfied with the use of money during my trip in Panglao.	4.56	Very Satisfied	4.5
10. The safety measures implemented in Panglao is satisfactory.	4.67	Very Satisfied	2
Composite Mean	4.56	Very Satisfied	

Legend:

4.20-5.00 - Very Satisfied

1.80-2.59 - Dissatisfied

3.40-4.19 - Satisfied

1.00-1.79 - Very Dissatisfied

2.60-3.39 - Neutral

Table 8 shows the Satisfaction of American Tourists' Amidst New Normal. Notably, Statement 8, 'The cleanliness and maintenance of the places I visited made me satisfied,' obtained the highest weighted mean of 4.69, signifying that American tourists are 'Very Satisfied' with the cleanliness and upkeep of Panglao's attractions. Conversely, Statement 2, 'I am satisfied with the accommodations I stayed at during my trip,' received the lowest weighted mean of 4.42, though it still indicates 'Very Satisfied'. The overall weighted mean for all statements is 4.56, with a descriptive value of 'Very Satisfied.' This implies that American tourists have enjoyed a successful and enjoyable experience in Panglao. These positive experiences are likely to translate into positive reviews, recommendations, and potentially repeat visits, ultimately benefiting the local tourism industry and supporting its growth in the long term.

The substantial influx of American tourists to the Philippines in 2022, with approximately 505.1 thousand travelers, underscores the pivotal role of the American market in Philippine tourism. This prominent presence of American tourists is indicative of the country's appeal and attraction to travelers from the United States. However, it's important to note that the COVID-19 pandemic severely disrupted the travel industry, resulting in a notable reduction in international tourist arrivals in 2021. As the tourism sector seeks to recover, it will be essential for the Philippines to prioritize and enhance the satisfaction of American tourists, given their significant contribution to the industry and the potential for their continued support in revitalizing the country's tourism sector (Mondares, 2023).

Table 9 represents the Tourists' Expenditures of Americans Amidst New Normal. The highest-rated aspect in the survey was "I am satisfied with my overall stay," with a score of 4.58. The lowest-rated aspect in the survey was "The fairness of pricing for buying gifts/souvenirs here is satisfactory," which received a score of 4.31. It is categorized as "Very Satisfied," indicating that tourists generally found the pricing for gifts and souvenirs to be fair. Overall, the tourists had a positive travel experience in regard to their expenditures, with a composite mean score of 4.47, categorizing their satisfaction level as "Very Satisfied". This indicates that the generally positive travel experience of tourists regarding their expenditures for gifts and souvenirs may require attention from entrepreneurs to enhance both their businesses and the satisfaction of tourists, considering it was the lowest-rated aspect in the survey, despite being categorized as "Very Satisfied".

The pandemic's economic impact has led to a shift in behavior largely attributed to budget constraints and financial considerations of American tourists in the Philippines. Tourists are now prioritizing price over service quality when making travel decisions. They are more likely to seek cost-effective travel options and value-for-money experiences while being mindful of their expenditures (Allan et al., 2022).

Table 9
Expenditures of American Tourists' Amidst New Normal
(N=55)

Statements	WM	DV	RANK
1. The reasonable food prices make me satisfied.	4.44	Very Satisfied	7
2. The affordability of transportation to Panglao compared to other tourist destinations leaves me satisfied.	4.36	Very Satisfied	9
3. The fairness of pricing for buying gifts/souvenirs here is satisfactory.	4.31	Very Satisfied	10
4. The prices of hotels left me satisfied.	4.53	Very Satisfied	4.5
5. The cost of island hopping is what I am satisfied with.	4.50	Very Satisfied	6
6. The favorable pricing of additional offers and handcraft products at this tourist destination satisfies me.	4.53	Very Satisfied	4.5
7. Staying at Panglao is worth every peso paid.	4.56	Very Satisfied	2.5
8. The nature of services makes me find them satisfying.	4.39	Very Satisfied	8
9. The belief that Panglao values my money and offers fair pricing is what I find.	4.56	Very Satisfied	2.5
10. I am satisfied with my overall stay.	4.58	Very Satisfied	1
Composite Mean	4.47	Very Satisfied	

Legend:

4.20-5.00 - Very Satisfied	1.80-2.59 - Dissatisfied
3.40-4.19 - Satisfied	1.00-1.79 - Very Dissatisfied
2.60-3.39 - Neutral	

Table 10 shows the computed r value of 0.5324 which is greater than the critical value of 0.1463 and the computed p value of < 0.00001. The value indicated that the null hypothesis is to be rejected. This further implies a strong positive correlation (r = 0.5324) between the variables. The critical r value of ± 0.1463 signifies the statistical significance ($p < 0.00001$) of the relationship and rejecting the null hypothesis (H_0). This is significant for further investigation to understand the nature and real-world implications of this relationship between the tourists' satisfaction and their expenditures.

Table 10
Significant Relationship Between Tourist Satisfaction and
Expenditures Amidst New normal
(N=180)

Relationship	Computed r	Critical r value	P - value	Decision
Tourists' Satisfaction VS Expenditures	0.5324	± 0.1463	< 0.00001	Reject Ho

Restaurants and other businesses can consider the accommodations for tourists by preparing a risk management plan to pursue their operations and adapt to the new normal. In the new normal of travel, tourists seek reassurance that their health and safety are a top priority. Businesses that proactively address these concerns by implementing measures such as enhanced sanitation protocols, physical distancing arrangements, and flexible booking options not only mitigate risks but also contribute to a more enjoyable and stress-free experience for tourists (Martín et al., 2022).

DISCUSSION

Findings

Based on the data gathered, the following emerged which served as bases for making the following:

1. Respondents' Profile

On Age. Most of the respondents are comprised of young adults from 18 years old to 35 years old, followed by adults from 36 years old, and then only a few from 50 years old above.

On Gender. In terms of gender, the respondents were half between males and females, with males having a few more than females.

On Nationality. Almost half of the respondents were led by Filipinos, followed by Americans, and then Koreans.

2. Respondents' Satisfaction

On Satisfaction. It indicated that Panglao is an extraordinarily appealing tourist location. This pleasant impression is likely to result in great evaluations and enthusiastic recommendations, perhaps generating increasing visitor numbers.

On Filipino Tourists. While tourists in the Philippines usually express a high degree of overall satisfaction with their experiences during the new normal, implied that there is potential for improvement in areas like as lodgings, transportation, and recommendations to others.

On Korean Tourists. This Indicated that Korean visitors had a fantastic time, which likely contributed to favorable evaluations and future repeat trips.

On American Tourists. This indicated that American visitors had a successful and delightful trip to Panglao. These favorable experiences are likely to transfer into positive evaluations, recommendations, and maybe future trips, ultimately benefiting and boosting the local tourist industry's long-term growth.

3. Respondents' Expenditures

On Expenditures. Respondents evaluated Panglao's transportation affordability to be satisfactory in comparison to comparable tourist locations.

On Filipino Tourists. This indicated that travelers are generally satisfied with their experiences, which can help Panglao's reputation as a tourist destination.

On Korean Tourists. This indicated that Panglao's reputation for clear and affordable pricing is an asset, presumably promoting confidence and loyalty among tourists.

On American Tourists. This indicated that the generally positive travel experience of tourists regarding their expenditures for gifts and souvenirs may require attention from entrepreneurs to enhance both their businesses and tourist satisfaction.

Conclusion

The researchers reached a conclusion that there is a strong correlation between tourists' satisfaction and expenditures, indicating that the experiences they have during their stay, as well as their spending habits in the new normal, significantly impact their overall well-being. This emphasizes the importance of factoring in tourists' socio-emotional well-being when planning their trips, recognizing the profound influence of their experiences and spending habits on their holistic welfare.

Recommendations

Based on the conclusions drawn from our comprehensive analysis, the following recommendations are proposed to enhance tourists' satisfaction and expenditures in Panglao, Bohol:

1.The Private Sectors and Local Government Unit (LGU) may invest in upgrading transportation systems to enhance accessibility for tourists, including efficient shuttle services and improved connectivity to key destinations to reduce travel times, making the region more attractive to visitors.

2.Business owners in Panglao may implement a tiered pricing approach catering to tourists with varying budgets, encompassing both budget-friendly and luxury options in accommodation, dining, and activities to ensure that all tourists find value in their expenditures.

3.The Department of Tourism may embrace sustainable tourism practices to preserve the natural beauty of the region, including implementing eco-friendly measures such as beach clean-up programs, waste reduction, and responsible wildlife encounters to attract eco conscious travelers and ensure the long-term sustainability of the destination.

4.The Local Government Union may promote cultural showcases, art exhibitions, and recreational activities to diversify the tourist experience and extend their stay. By offering engaging and culturally enriching activities, Panglao can encourage tourists to spend more time and resources in the region, benefiting local businesses and enhancing the overall visitor experience.

Compliance with Ethical Standards

This study adhered to ethical standards by obtaining informed consent from all participants, ensuring confidentiality, and maintaining voluntary participation without coercion. No harm came to participants, and the study received ethics committee approval. Researchers declared no conflicts of interest and reported findings transparently and honestly. Cultural sensitivity was respected throughout the research process.

PROPOSED IMPROVEMENT PLAN OF TOURISTS' SATISFACTION AND EXPENDITURES AMIDST NEW NORMAL

Rationale

The COVID-19 pandemic has significantly impacted the tourism sector worldwide, and Panglao is no exception. By implementing this plan, local stakeholders and officials can proactively tackle these challenges and ensure the sustainability and growth of tourism in the area. Regulating pricing practices is crucial for building tourists' trust and confidence in the destination. Fair and transparent pricing practices will not only benefit tourists but also contribute to the long-term success of local businesses.

Prioritizing health and safety measures is essential for Panglao to adapt to the "new normal". Furthermore, continuous awareness campaigns will help educate both locals and tourists about the importance of adhering to health and safety guidelines, creating a sense of responsibility and cooperation within the community. Maintaining high quality standards is paramount for attracting and retaining tourists. Cleanliness and exceptional service will not only satisfy tourists but also generate positive reviews and word-of-mouth recommendations, further enhancing Panglao's reputation as a preferred destination. This will ultimately lead to increased tourist satisfaction and expenditures, contributing to the economic growth and development of the region.

Objectives

This study aims to explicitly realize the following goals:

- To evaluate tourist satisfaction within the new normal by examining contributing factors, overall satisfaction levels, and segment-specific variations.
- To examine the influence of the new normal on tourists' spending habits by investigating the effects of travel restrictions, health protocols, and safety measures and by comparing pre-pandemic and post-pandemic expenditure trends to assess their economic implications on the tourism industry.
- To investigate the correlation between tourist satisfaction and expenditures in the new normal, analyzing whether higher satisfaction levels are associated with increased spending and identifying the specific factors that shape this relationship within the current travel environment.
- To provide recommendations for stakeholders in the tourism industry, this objective seeks to offer actionable insights to enhance tourist satisfaction and stimulate spending in the "new normal." It also aims to suggest adaptive strategies that align with changing consumer preferences and expectations within the post-pandemic tourism landscape.

Mechanics of Implementation

Before putting their plans into action, the researchers need to make sure that the proposed improvement plan has been shared with and evaluated by the research panel.

This step is vital as the panelists' guidance, recommendations, and insights will significantly contribute to enhancing and elucidating the intended deliverables. Once the researchers obtain approval from the panelists, they can proceed with confidence.

Schedule of Implementation

After the proposed program has been approved by the authorities in charge, researchers must submit the improvement plan to the relevant authorities, informing them of the study's findings and recommendations. Once authorization is granted, the program can be implemented.

Monitoring and Evaluation

A monitoring and evaluation tool will be adapted to assess how the tourist satisfaction and expenditures within the new normal can be optimized. Regular assessments will be conducted by the researchers to identify areas of concern among tourists, aiming to improve their overall experience and enhance the financial impact on the local economy. This process will ensure that the tourism strategy aligns with the evolving needs of travelers in this changed environment.

REFERENCES

- Allan, G., Connolly, K., Figus, G., & Maurya, A. (2022). Economic impacts of COVID-19 on inbound and domestic tourism. *Annals of Tourism Research Empirical Insights*, 3(2), 100075.
- Bohol tourist arrivals up by 129% in first 5 months. (2023, July 5). BOHOLCHRONICLE.COM.PH. <https://www.boholchronicle.com.ph/2023/07/05/bohol-tourist-arrivals-up-by-129-in-first-5-months/>
- Department of Tourism. (2022, May 6). Domestic travel to drive recovery of tourism industry, says survey - Love the Philippines! Welcome to the DOT's Corporate Site. Love the Philippines! Welcome to the DOT's Corporate Site. https://beta.tourism.gov.ph/news_and_updates/domestic-travel-to-drive-recovery-of-tourism-industry-says-survey/
- Department of Tourism-Philippines. (2021). Tourism.gov.ph. http://tourism.gov.ph/news_features/BaliksaBohol.aspx
- Estremera, R. (n.d.). Organizational resilience and impacts of the COVID-19 pandemic on Philippine businesses. <https://www2.upmin.edu.ph/index.php/news-sp-5975/5288-organizational-resilience-and-impacts-of-the-covid-19-pandemic-on-philippine-businesses>
- Fatmawati, I., & Olga, F. (2023). Investigating the determining factors of tourist revisit intention in a natural-based tourism destination. *E3S Web of Conferences*, 444, 01014. <https://doi.org/10.1051/e3sconf/202344401014>
- Gök, T., & Sayın, K. (2015). South Korean tourists' expectation, satisfaction and loyalty relationship. ResearchGate. https://www.researchgate.net/publication/357936251_South_Korean_Tourists'_Expectation_Satisfaction_and_Loyalty_Relationship

- Ledesma, J. V., Penetrante, M. O. T., & Hernandez, C. N. (2022). Determinants of tourists' satisfaction: The case of DOT accredited accommodation establishments in the Province of Capiz, Philippines. *Central Philippine University Multidisciplinary Research Journal*, 1(1), 14-24.
- Macasero, R. (2022, August 3). Panglao tourism council proposes ban on selling food in Virgin Island. *RAPPLER*. <https://www.rappler.com/philippines/visayas/panglao-tourism-council-proposes-ban-selling-food-virgin-island/>
- Martín, J. C., Saayman, M., & du Plessis, E. (2019). Determining satisfaction of international tourist: A different approach. *Journal of Hospitality and Tourism Management*, 40, 1-10.
- Philippine News Agency. (2023). PH targets 4.8M visitor arrivals, \$5.8-B tourism revenue in 2023. <https://www.pna.gov.ph/articles/1191096>
- Philippine Statistics Authority. (2023, June 15). Tourism contributes 6.2 percent to GDP in 2022 | Philippine Statistics Authority | Republic of the Philippines. <https://psa.gov.ph/content/tourism-contributes-62-percent-gdp-2022>
- Republic Act No. 7394 | GOVPH. (1992, April 13). Official Gazette of the Republic of the Philippines. <https://www.officialgazette.gov.ph/1992/04/13/republic-act-no-7394-s-1992/>
- Republic Act No. 9593 | GOVPH. (2009, May 12). Official Gazette of the Republic of the Philippines. <https://www.officialgazette.gov.ph/2009/05/12/republic-act-no-9593-s-2009/>
- Rohman, F. (2020). Determining adventure tourist loyalty: Mediating role of tourist satisfaction and quality of life. *The Journal of Asian Finance, Economics and Business*, 7(10), 255-265.
- Roxas, F. M. Y., Rivera, J. P. R., & Gutierrez, E. L. M. (2020). Framework for creating sustainable tourism using systems thinking. *Current Issues in Tourism*, 23(3), 280-296.